

IoT and lighting control for smart greenhouse

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Abstract— This article presents the development of an optimal lighting system for greenhouses, allowing uniform illumination over the entire greenhouse surface and meeting the plants' needs in terms of PFFD. Our work aims to develop a control system that is based on the use of a light sensor, a dimmable luminaire, a RASPBERRY PI 3 and a web application. The brightness management is done in an autonomous and/or manual way according to the user's choice, the automatic control uses the data from the lighting sensors, However, the user can opt for the manual control to vary the luminous intensity of the luminaires. The system was designed, prototyped, and tested in Tunis province of Tunisia. Our contribution through this work represents the management of agriculture through digital innovation (IoT) to optimize the lighting energy used in greenhouses through the use of the Daylight system control technique and the combination of biological parameters that define tomato lighting requirements and DLI to analyze the measured data to choose the best control mode. All this has allowed us not only to supervise, control and reduce the energy cost of lighting, but also to improve the productivity and quality of tomatoes.

Keywords— IOT; LED luminaire; Raspberry Pi; Smart Greenhouse; Web application.

I. INTRODUCTION

Digitation and the technical evolution of systems have made very remarkable progress during this decade, they have quickly penetrated into our daily lives as well as into several sectors of activity such as industrial activities, transport, medical, agriculture, etc...

Especially in the field of greenhouse agriculture, digitation has enabled its users to improve the productivity and profitability of their systems.

Greenhouses are traditionally controlled by ON/OFF buttons through the control panel which is usually placed inside the greenhouse however this traditional method is not efficient and requires the presence of the user to perform the control.

The technology subsequently evolved through the use of time-delay systems [1-3] but unfortunately, this method does not provide accurate, reliable and efficient control, nor does it allow data to be recorded in order to be able to analyse them and detect more effective control methods.

The Greenhouse Control Mode underwent a radical evolution a few years later using programmable controllers or microcontrollers connected to sensors for data acquisition and has relays for control [4-9]. Unfortunately, this method

remains limited and ineffective as it has not solved the problem of data recording and management as mentioned by [10-12].

Nowadays greenhouse control is done through the Internet of Things (IoT).

The IoT is essentially composed of three main technologies:

(1) a sensor for data acquisition,

(2) a network for data communication between the connected objects and the computer.

(3) the computer that ensures the analysis and intelligent processing of the various data to convert them into control actions.

The IoT has covered almost all areas of agriculture (irrigation, temperature control, humidity control, etc.).

In irrigation, a system has been created to control the water pumps when the humidity level decreases in relation to the user's set point by using sensors for reading the humidity, relays for activating and deactivating the pumps [13].

In temperature and humidity control, [14] has developed a system using an Arduino board capable of monitoring and controlling the ambient humidity, soil moisture, and temperature of a greenhouse in the Valeriana jatamansi area.

In the control and monitoring of air quality and CO₂ [15] has implemented a system that automatically monitors and controls air quality parameters and co₂ inside greenhouses.

All these systems have improved the efficiency of greenhouse control and monitoring, however, there are a few parameters that haven't been considered in the works of the majority of author and which has, directly and indirectly, impact on the energy balance of the greenhouse and which require more emphasis such as lighting, we have shown in a previous article[16] that this parameter is essential to ensure optimal plant growth and that we can make significant energy savings if we manage to optimise the monitoring and control of this factor and this is the subject of our study and contribution.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. System Overview

We aim to design and implement a lighting control system using sensors spread over nine different locations in the greenhouse, to collect the different levels of illumination and

transmit them to the RASPBERRY PI who will process this data and the stocks in the web application database.

The farmer will then be able to handle the greenhouse remotely through a control panel designated to communicate with the RASPBERRY PI, the control panel is a web application accessible via the Internet or via the local network of the greenhouse that offers several features for better accessibility to the greenhouse,

we can present an overview of our system as shown in Figure.1.

Figure.1. System Overview

B. System Design

Our system is essentially composed of 3 components:

- The TSL2561 illuminance sensors, which measure illuminance in real-time.
- The RASPBERRY PI which allows controlling the luminous intensity of the luminaires inside the greenhouse.
- The web application: allows us to monitor and manage IoT information in real-time.

1) IoT devices

During our design we used the TSL2561 sensor which is a very light-sensitive sensor and allows to calculate the amount of visible and infrared light, it communicates with the RASPBERRY PI through the i2c bus.

The characteristics of the TSL2561 sensor are shown in Table I.

TABLE I: TSL2561 CHARACTERISTICS

Power supply	2,7 à 3,6 Vcc
Interface	I2C
Measuring range:	0,1 à 40000 Lux
T° of service:	-30 à +80 °C

2) Design of the control system (RASPBERRY PI):

The control system is developed with the PYTHON language and the MYSQL language,

The control system can communicate with the database peripherals, as well as actuators:

- Interaction control unit /database:

The control system communicates with the database in order to extract the necessary information for good management of the greenhouse however the MYSQLDB library allows to interact with the database management

system, the interaction activity diagram of the control unit /database is presented as shown in Figure.2.

Figure 2. Activity diagram interaction of the control unit/database

- Interaction control unit/peripherals:

The manipulation of hardware resources such as communication buses, input/output ports requires the use of libraries to communicate with external devices, the interaction activity diagram of the control unit/peripherals is presented as shown in Figure.3.

Figure 3. Activity diagram interaction of the control unit and peripherals

- Interaction control unit/actuators:

The control system uses the data retrieved from the database to control the actuators, the figure .4. presents the interaction activity diagram of the control unit/actuators.

Figure 4. Activity diagram interaction of the control unit/actuator

to simplify all this, we can present the use case diagram of our control system as shown in Figure 5.

Figure.5. RASPBERRY PI user case diagram

3) Design of the web application

The SMART GREENHOUSE web application was developed with HTML5, CSS3, JAVASCRIPT, PHP5 languages, and to accelerate the application development process and obtain an ergonomically optimized web application, we have used BOOTSTRAP which is a FRAMEWORK of CSS and JAVASCRIPT in order to well organize the different parts of the web pages, we have also used a FRAMEWORK of JAVASCRIPT called JQUERY and which is very useful to interact with web servers as well as to execute a diversity of events according to the results received from the server.

The interaction with the database server is an essential task, and to do this it is necessary to develop files called server files with the PHP language that allows being an intermediary between the client and the server, there is also some functionality that uses JQUERY libraries or PHP libraries in order to trace curve and to generate PDF files containing greenhouse data. We can present the case diagram of our application and its graphical interface as shown respectively in Figures 6-9.

Figure.6. The control panel of the application

Figure.7. Plant management

Figure.8. Control mode of the greenhouse

Figure.9. The dashboard of the web application

C. Implementation

In our study we used nine TSL2561 light sensors which are associated respectively to nine luminaires group as shown in Figure 10., and which are connected to a RASPBERRY PI3 in order to transmit the value of the illumination in real-time, the RASPBERRY PI stores this data and the data. processed to calculate the difference between the daylight and our target which is 8475 LUX [16] in order to control the luminaire to obtain a uniform illumination equal to the desired value at any time "t".

As detailed in our previous article [16] the luminaire will be switched of while the target is achieved and to be turn on (60w) when the illumination is 0 lux and dimmed if the illumination is]0 – 8475[.

The RASPBERRY PI 3 will control the luminaires through a PWM signal control to attenuate or increase their light intensities for a duration of 16h as long as the DLI is lower than the target value of the tomato plant [16] but once the DLI is reached RASPBERRY PI controls the fixture group associated with this sensor to be in the off state,

The figures 11-13 represent a practical test on the behavior of the system for a single sensor to show the different real-time measurements such as power [w], lighting [lux], ect ...

Figure.10. Distribution of sensors and luminaire groups inside the greenhouse

Figure 10 represents the position and the associated number of each sensors and luminaire groups inside the greenhouse.

Figure.11. System Implementation

Figure.12. Measurement of the illumination and the power consumption of the luminaire – Test 1.

Figure.13. Measurement of the illumination and the power consumption of the luminaire – Test 2.

Figure 11 represent the practical test used for the measurement of the illumination measured by the sensor and the power consumption of the controlled luminaire.

Figure 12 and Figure 13 represent two simple test, where the first one shows an illumination of 3248 Lux for a power consumption of 37w and the second one an illumination of 4949 Lux for a power consumption of 25w, these results are expected and confirms that's our system is working correctly.

System data analysis

The illumination data of each sensor are recorded and stored in a daily manner, Figure 14 shows the illumination data measured for the various sensors during 16h while Figure 15 represents the data of the DLI.

Figure.14. Evolution of the illumination from 7h:00 to 21h:00 for the day 15-06-2019

Figure.15. Evolution of the measured DLI from 7h:00 to 12h:15 for the day 15-06-2019

Figures 14 and 15, represent the evolution of the illumination from 7:00 am to 9:00 pm and the DLI measured up to 12:15 in the nine different zones, it is clear that we do not have the same measurements and this is expected, as the value of the illumination is not the same as a function of time and place, the difference can reach 12% by comparing the results obtained by the sensors 5 and 6 with those measured by the sensor 2, these values depend essentially from several parameters such as the shape of the greenhouse, the angle of inclination of the sun, the position and direction of the

greenhouse, altitude, latitude, etc. This difference has a direct effect on the consumption of fixtures and indirectly on the energy balance of the greenhouse as we have shown in a previous article [16]. This difference has a direct effect on the consumption of luminaires and an indirect effect on the greenhouse balance energy as we have shown in a previous article [16]. To compare the daily consumption of the lighting system by adapting traditional lighting control systems with our IoT control system,

Traditional control systems generally use timers that adopt one of these two control strategies (control scenario 1 and control scenario 2) respectively:

Light one hour before the sunset until midnight [17] i.e. from 6:30 p.m. until midnight, which means a total of 5h:30 of additional lighting,

Light 4-5 hours of sunset until 1h after the sunrise [17], i.e. from 23:30 to 5:30 am, which mean a total of 6h:30 of additional lighting,

In order to deduce the energy gain, we have superimposed the consumption curves relating to the traditional control modes 1 and 2 as well as the groups of luminaires associated with the sensor 2 and 6 as represented in figure.16.

Figure.16. Lighting Power consumption [%]

According to Figure 16, we notice that the group of luminaires associated with sensor 6 consumes less than the “1/5” of the energy required compared to the groups of luminaires associated with the sensor 2, we also note that through our system, we can save up to 58% of energy compared to traditional control mode. We have therefore not only succeeded in satisfying the DLI condition and guaranteeing the same growth rate of the various plants but also in optimising the energy consumption of the luminaires.

III. CONCLUSION

This research has shown that the supervision and control of lighting can improve the efficiency of our greenhouse in terms of consumption and quality of products. We have naturally drawn the following conclusions:

- The average illumination differs from one area to another and this has been shown through the installation of nine sensors inside our greenhouse, this difference is essentially due to several parameters such as (greenhouse position, altitude, latitude, geometric shape of the greenhouse, angle of inclination of the sun, etc.....) [16].

- The control of the luminaires allowed us to have a uniform illumination and distributed in the same way in order to guarantee a better quality of product and which has the same growth.
- Our system, allows us to control our greenhouse manually and/or automatically, it eventually solved the data logging problem which will allow us to analyze the data in real-time and gives us the opportunity to improve our system in a continuous way.
- Our contribution on the reduction of the energy consumption of luminaires and hours of operation has allowed us to reduce the consumption of 12% from one zone to another (zone 5 and zone 6 Versus zone 2) and 58% compared to traditional control mode (Zone 6 Vs control scenario 2).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I gratefully acknowledge the support and generosity of BBL institute, without which the present study could not have been completed.

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